

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_LSM_50x_natural_e_Topo		
Created on:	4/13/2021 2:00:09 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	67.06	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	1.023	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\Dropbox\jmmarreir...x_natural_e_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/13/2021 2:00:09 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	20.29	μm	
Min:	-11.1	μm	
Max:	9.187	μm	
Size:	198268	digits	
Spacing:	0.1023	nm	
NM-points ratio:	63.90 % (5750760 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/13/2021 2:00:09 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	20.29	μm	
Size:	198268	digits	
Spacing:	0.1023	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	3.411	μm	
Ssk	-0.3316		
Sku	3.249		
Sp	9.042	μm	
Sv	11.25	μm	
Sz	20.29	μm	
Sa	2.672	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	0.3459	%	
Smc	4.248	μm	
Sxp	7.781	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	27.90	μm	
Str	*****		
Std	176.7	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.6878		
Sdr	16.57	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.1409	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vv	4.389	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmp	0.1409	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmc	3.007	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvc	3.940	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvv	0.4482	μm ³ /μm ²	

Analyses:	
ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

Warnings

Str: The autocorrelation lobe touches the edges. Try to level the...

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	9.297	µm
Mean depth of furrows	3.052	µm
Mean density of furrows	4351	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	0.02336	°
Second direction	135.0	°
Third direction	90.01	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	65.33	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

